

Synthesis and structure of some cobalt(III) complexes with azide, dimethylglyoxime and heterocyclic nitrogen donor ligands

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A series of new hydrogen bonded *trans*-azidocobaloxime of the type [Co(DH)₂N₃L] where DH = dimethylglyoximate anion, L = [pyridine, piperidine, piperazine, quinoline, iso-quinoline, triazole, indole, benzimidazole, benzotriazole, or carbazole] have been prepared by passing air in cobalt(II) acetate, sodium azide, dimethylglyoxime and heterocyclic nitrogen donor ligands in ethanol medium. The complexes are characterized by UV, IR, NMR spectra. The thermogravimetric analyses indicate that these compounds are quite stable upto 200° and never associated with solvent or water molecules.

The cobaloxime of cobalt(III) complexes are of interest from both the chemical and biological¹⁻³ point of view. They closely stimulate the reaction of vitamin B₁₂ and are also important in vitamin B₁₂ model chemistry. The X-ray crystal structure of alkyl-cobaloximes suggest that the cobalt atom in cobaloxime has slightly greater positive charge causing relatively stronger attachment of a base along the axial direction. From our point of view it was challenging to study the interaction between metal ions and heterocyclic nitrogen compounds, that occur in living systems and are used as medicaments. It is also well known that heterocyclic compounds play a significant role in many biological systems, especially six-membered ring system being a component of several vitamins and drugs. It is known that some drugs act via chelation or via the inhabitation of metalloenzymes, but little is known about the modification activity of most drugs when their legating potential is utilized. The interaction of cobalt(III) atom, which plays a vital role in a number of quite different biological processes, is a subject of considerable interest. We report here the synthesis of cobaloximes containing N-donor ligands as axial ligands and linear triatomic azide ion N⁻³ in sixth^{4,5} coordination position.

Results and discussion

The unidentate nitrogen donor ligands (pyridine, piperidine, piperazine, quinoline, iso-quinoline, triazole, indole, benzimidazole, benzotriazole, carbazole) react (*in situ*) with Co (N₃)₂ dimethylglyoxime in presence of air to form a

series of azido-cobaloxime [Co(DH)₂N₃L] which are presented in Table 1 along with their analytical and other characterising data.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of [Co(DH)₂N₃L] complexes*

Compd.	Decomp. temp. °C	Cobalt%: Found (Calcd.)
A = Co(DH) ₂ N ₃		
[A (py)] pyridine	210	14.40 (14.39)
[A (pi)] piperidine	216	14.22 (14.18)
[A (pip)] piperazine	>240	14.15 (14.14)
[A (qui)] quinoline	208	12.86 (12.82)
[A (iso-qui)] iso-quinoline	212	12.86 (12.83)
[A (tria)] triazole	205	14.73 (14.75)
[A (ind)] indole	>240	13.15 (13.16)
[A (bmz)] benzimidazole	>240	13.15 (13.14)
[A (btz)] benzotriazole	>240	13.12 (13.11)
[A (car)] carbazole	>240	11.19 (11.18)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses

These compounds are stable, non-electrolytes in dilute solution on 10⁻³ M of MeNO₂. The molar conductance values in nitromethane are in the range of 10–25 mhos cm² mol⁻¹. It shows that these compounds do not loose indole or other nitrogen containing ligands, or azide in the solution. The electronic spectra in DMSO shows the spin allowed ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{1g} transition in the region 18000 to 20000 cm⁻¹, the ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{2g} band is masked by the intense charge

transfer bands. A band appeared at 40000 cm^{-1} . It is due to intra-ligand $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition of the coordinated dimethylglyoxime. The band occurring at 28000 cm^{-1} , is assigned to the indole \rightarrow Co (LMCT) and band at 33000 cm^{-1} is due to $d\pi(\text{Co}) \rightarrow \pi^*(\text{DH})$ (MLCT) transition. The last absorption at 32000 cm^{-1} is assigned to intra-ligand CT absorption in N_3^- .

The important IR bands of azido cobaloximes are discussed. The free uncoordinated dimethylglyoxime has no band at 1240 cm^{-1} . In case of $\text{Ni}(\text{DH})_2$ complexes a strong band appeared at 1240 cm^{-1} due to the $\nu_{\text{N-O}}$ of ionised N-OH grouping of the dimethylglyoxime⁹. In this present case this band seen at 1234 to 1240 cm^{-1} and additional band $\nu_{\text{N-O}}$ appears at 1090 to 1101 cm^{-1} . This indicates that N-O bond of the coordinated DH^- are not entirely equivalent. This observation is consistent with the result of X-ray diffraction analysis of the $\text{Cu}(\text{DH})_2$ complexes in which two different Cu-N distances were observed. The stretching vibration $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ of these complexes appears at 1595 to 1605 cm^{-1} . A very weak intensity band observed in the region 1700 to 1800 cm^{-1} is attributed to the deformation mode of the strong intra molecular hydrogen bridge. The bond at around 3417 to 3440 cm^{-1} is assigned for intra molecular hydrogen bonding in the complexes. All these suggest the *trans*-configuration¹⁰ of the complexes. The characteristic bands $\nu_{\text{Co-N}}$ (N of DH) appears at 570 cm^{-1} . The second band for metal to nitrogen bonding $\nu_{\text{Co-N}}$ (N of carbazole or other ligands) appears¹¹ at 439 to 445 cm^{-1} .

The azide ion has cylindrical shape. It is linear symmetric triatomic system with sixteen valency electrons, are of interest. Two bands appear at 650 to 660 cm^{-1} and 2020 to 2030 cm^{-1} . The first is bending mode and second one is stretching mode of the azide group. The X-ray crystal structure of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3]^{2+}$ has shown that the N_3^- group is bent at angle of 124.8° to the Co-N axis with a slightly greater $\text{N}_1\text{-N}_2$ bond length (1.21 \AA) as compared to the $\text{N}_2\text{-N}_3$ bond length (1.14 \AA).

¹H NMR spectra :

The NMR (¹H) spectra have also been used in elucidating the metal to ligand interaction and stereochemistry of the complexes. The *trans* structure of cobaloxime would render the four methyl group equivalent, resulting only one signal¹². The hydrogens of methyl group in free dimethylglyoxime give singlet at 1.98 ppm . The present complex shows that this singlet δ shifts down field and appears at around 2.5 ppm . The PMR chemical shifts δ of carbazole or other nitrogen donor ligand move down field and generally appears at around 7.12 to 8.11 ppm . In free carbazole δ for H-1 generally appears at 7 ppm . In the complexes this

signal δ shifted down field and appears at 7.12 ppm . The signal δ for H-3, H-4 in free ligand appears at 7.39 ppm , on coordination this signal δ shifted down field and appears at 7.49 ppm . The signal δ for H-2, H-5 appears at 7.91 , on the complexes this signal δ shifted to 8.11 ppm . This conform the attachment of carbazole to the cobalt. The δ due to OH proton in the dimethylglyoxime appears at 11.33 ppm this signal shifted up field in the complexes and appears at around 11.23 ppm .

¹³C NMR spectra :

The ¹³C NMR spectra of the azide cobaloxime complexes containing indole or other related axial ligand are assigned. The oxime CH_3 carbon in free DH_2 generally appears at 9.2 ppm . On coordination, this signal shifted down field and appear as a very sharp singlet signal at 12.82 ppm in all the complexes. The imine carbon in the complexes appears at around 151.8 ppm uniformly which is slightly up field compared to the value of 153.0 ppm in free dimethylglyoxime. The ¹³C NMR signal of axial ligand undergoes down field shift generally appears at around 39 to 41 ppm . The individual peak for carbon in the heterocyclic nitrogen donor ligands can not be ascertained due to limitation of our instrument. For axial ligand we got a broad peak in every complexes.

$[\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{N}_3\text{L}]$

DH = dimethylglyoximate anion, L = heterocyclic nitrogen donor ligands.

All these observation show the *trans* structure of the azido cobaloxime complexes. The thermal decomposition of the $[\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{N}_3\text{pi}]$ have been investigated in a atmosphere of nitrogen in the temperature range 25 to 1000° by means of TG and DTA.

The TG curve indicates that it is thermally stable up to 194.07°. Afterwards the TG curve shows four weight loss steps. The first step takes place at 194.07° and is accompanied by 2.43% weight loss. This is attributed to loss of ten hydrogen atom from piperidine molecules. The second step of decomposition between (194.07–287.82°) is accompanied by 57.71% weight loss. This step may be due the loss of remaining part of piperidine molecules, one DMG ion and 60% of another DMG ion. The third step (287.82–569.07°) is accompanied by 19.7% weight loss. This loss of mass may be due to removal of azide ion and 30% of DMG ion. The last step (569.07–920°) of decomposition is associated with 5% weight loss. In this step the remaining part of the compound is converted to metallic oxide.

The DTA curve for the complex $[\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{N}_3\text{pi}]$ exhibits two endothermic peak at 210° and 930°, corresponding to the loss of ten hydrogen atom and 20% of remaining dimethylglyoxime. At this temperature the compound is converted to metallic oxide. This curve also contain two exothermic maxima with centres at about 286° and 569° corresponding to the loss of piperidine molecule and azide ion respectively.

However other complexes are stable up to 200°. This indicates the absence of water of crystallisation or association of solvent molecules. After 200° the heterocyclic nitrogen donor ligands are removed followed by dimethylglyoxime. The azide anion is removed at last. The last product of decomposition is Co_3O_4 .

Experimental

Cobalt(II) acetate, dimethylglyoxime (Dmg) carbazole, isoquinoline (all E. Merck), sodium azide (B.D.H.), pyridine, piperidine, indole, benzimidazole, benzotriazole, triazole (all SD Fine Chemicals), quinoline, piperazine (Loba) were used.

$[\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{N}_3\text{L}]$: Sodium azide (0.3 g, 4.2 mmol) was added to the stirring solution of $\text{Co}(\text{ac})_2 \cdot 4 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.5 g, 2 mmol) in EtOH (25 ml). After 5 min dimethylglyoxime (0.5 g, 4.3 mmol) was added to this mixture, heated and stirred for 45 min. The brown solution obtained, was filtered. The indole (4.2 mmol) or other nitrogen donor ligands [pyridine, piperidine, piperazine, quinoline, iso-quinoline, triazole, indole, benzimidazole, benzotriazole, carbazole] in 3 ml EtOH was added to the filtrate. The whole mixture

was warmed for 2 min and then cooled. A continuous stream of air was then bubbled through the solution for one hour. The deep reddish brown compound deposited at the bottom. It was collected on the frit, washed with EtOH several times followed by Et_2O . The product was finally dried *in vacuo*.

Cobalt contents were estimated gravimetrically. The C, H and N were estimated by a Carlo Erba-1108 analyser. Conductivity was measured by a Systronic 304 conductivity meter.

The UV spectra (DMSO) were recorded on a Hitachi-320-Perkin-Elmer Lambda-15 instrument, IR spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer and NMR spectra (DMSO- d_6) on a Bruker DRX-300 spectrometer using TMS as internal reference.

Thermal decomposition (TG and DTA) of the complexes were carried out by using Netzsch-Geratebau GmbH thermal analyzer. Measurements were carried out between room temperature and 1000° in an atmosphere of nitrogen at a heating of 10° min^{-1} .

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